

Supplementary information for:

Chickpea nodulation in Turkish field soils

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Released online 15 April 2026

Table S1 Province and localities of 180 samples assayed for chickpea and lentil nodulation with the number of positives (nodulation obtained) per locality.

Province	Region	Locality	Samples	Total	Chickpea		Lentil	
					Postives	Total	Postives	Total
Adana	Mediterranean	Çiçekli	1		1		1	
		Çirişgediği	3		3		3	
		Karayusuflu	4		4		4	
		Kargakekeç	3		3		3	
		Kepezetepe	1		1		1	
		Kılbaş	2	20	2	20	2	20
		Kırıklı	1		1		1	
		Sadıkali	2		2		2	
		Salbaş Esentepe	1		1		1	
		Topaktaş	1		1		1	
Gaziantep	Southeastern Anatolia	Yazıbaşı	1		1		1	
		Bağlarbaşı	2		2		2	
		Belören	2		1		2	
		Gedik	1		1		1	
		Geneyik	1		1		1	
		İkizkuyu	2		2		2	
		Karpuzkaya/ Şhitkamil	3	21	3	20	3	20
		Nurdağı	3		3		2	
		Yağdöver	2		2		2	
		Yığınlı	3		3		3	
Zeytinli	2		2		2			

Province	Region	Locality	Samples	Total	Chickpea		Lentil	
					Postives	Total	Postives	Total
Hatay	Mediterranean	Başpınar	2		2		2	
		Beşaslan	1		1		1	
		Çiloğlanhüyüğü	2		2		2	
		Doğuyarıncı	1		1		1	
		Gazimürseltepesi	1		1		1	
		Gündüz	1		1		1	
		Ilıkpınar	2		2		2	
		Kırcaoğlu	2		1		2	
		Konuk	2	21	1	19	2	20
		Kuletepe	1		1		1	
		Kurtlusoguksu	1		1		0	
		Mehmetbeyli	3		3		3	
		Özsoğuksu	1		1		1	
Topboğazı	1		1		1			
Kahramanmaraş	Mediterranean	Çiğli	2		2		1	
		Çınarlı	2		2		2	
		Dulkadiroğlu	3		3		3	
		Güzelyurt	2		2		2	
		Onikişubat	3	18	3	18	2	14
		Şekeroba	2		2		2	
		Seyrantepe	2		2		0	
		Suçatı	1		1		1	
Kayseri	Central Anatolia	Türkoğlu	1		1		1	
		Ağcaşar	2		2		2	
		Araplı	1		1		1	
		Bahçelievler	1		1		1	
		Denizovası	2		2		2	
		Güneyaşağı	2	21	2	17	2	16
		İçmece	4		2		3	
		Mustafabeyli	2		1		1	
		Sarıkürklü	4		3		1	
		Tashan	3		3		3	
Konya	Central Anatolia	Adalet/Karapınar	4		3		4	
		Akören	3		2		1	
		Bahçeli	1		1		1	
		Çengilti	1		1		1	
		İsmil/Karatay	2		1		1	
		Kargacı	4	20	4	16	4	17
		Ortakonak	1		1		1	
		Şatır	1		1		1	
		Sazlıpınar/Karapınar	1		0		1	
		Tatlacak	1		1		1	
Ziya Gökalp/Ereğli	1		1		1			

Province	Region	Locality	Samples	Total	Chickpea		Lentil	
					Postives	Total	Postives	Total
Nevşehir	Central Anatolia	Çakıllı	3		3		2	
		Demirci	1		1		1	
		Derinkuyu	3		3		3	
		Doğala	1		1		1	
		Kaymaklı	2	19	2	19	2	15
		Kurugöl	3		3		3	
		Özlüce	2		2		0	
		Suvermez	2		2		2	
		Yazıhüyük	2		2		1	
Niğde	Central Anatolia	Acıgöl/Bor	2		0		1	
		Altunhisar	2		1		2	
		Bağdüz/Bor	2		1		2	
		Çamardı	5	20	5	13	5	17
		Kaynarca/Bor	3		1		2	
		Merkez	2		2		2	
		Sağlık/Altunhisar	3		3		3	
		Sazlıca	1		0		0	
Osmaniye	Mediterranean	Ahmet Yesevi	2		2		2	
		Bahçe	1		1		1	
		Cevdetiye	3		2		2	
		Dervişli	2		2		2	
		Kesmeburun	1	20	1	19	1	19
		Kumarlı	3		3		3	
		Şekerdere	1		1		1	
		Tehçi	3		3		3	
		Tülücüler	2		2		2	
Yaverpaşa	2		2		2			
Overall total				180		161		158

Chickpea Fig. 3B

```
~~~~~
PlantDW ~ NodulesLg + Plants
~~~~~
```

```
Coefficients:
      Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.15234    0.24209   4.760 4.1e-06 ***
NodulesLg    0.88543    0.07718  11.472 < 2e-16 ***
Plants      -0.24846    0.12983  -1.914 0.0573 .
---

Residual standard error: 0.6218 on 171 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared: 0.4358, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4292
F-statistic: 66.04 on 2 and 171 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
NodulesLg  1  49.65  49.65 128.418 <2e-16 ***
Plants     1   1.42   1.42   3.663 0.0573 .
Residuals 171  66.11   0.39
---
```

Chickpea Fig. 3C

```
~~~~~
NodulesLg ~ Latitude + Plants
~~~~~
```

```
Coefficients:
      Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  8.12545    2.76578   2.938 0.00376 **
Latitude    -0.19802    0.07313  -2.708 0.00746 **
Plants       0.35763    0.12297   2.908 0.00412 **
---

Residual standard error: 0.6033 on 171 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared: 0.08987, Adjusted R-squared: 0.07922
F-statistic: 8.442 on 2 and 171 DF, p-value: 0.0003188

      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
Latitude  1   3.07  3.0667   8.427 0.00418 **
Plants    1   3.08  3.0779   8.457 0.00412 **
Residuals 171  62.23  0.3639
---
```

Chickpea Fig. 3D

```
~~~~~
NodulesLg ~ Longitude + Plants
~~~~~
```

```
Call:
lm(formula = model, data = data)

Residuals:
      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.60317 -0.33103  0.08212  0.39685  1.16741

Coefficients:
      Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) -7.60910    1.25689  -6.054 8.70e-09 ***
Longitude    0.23673    0.03547   6.674 3.33e-10 ***
Plants       0.29271    0.11237   2.605  0.01 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5487 on 171 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared: 0.247, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2382
F-statistic: 28.04 on 2 and 171 DF, p-value: 2.932e-11

      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
Longitude  1  14.84  14.844  49.299 4.96e-11 ***
Plants     1   2.04   2.043   6.785  0.01 *
Residuals 171  51.49   0.301
---
```

Lentil Fig. 4A

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~~~~~
NodulesLg ~ Crop + Plants
~~~~~

              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
Crop           3  7.826   2.6086   15.21 9.26e-09 ***
Plants         1  2.168   2.1681   12.64 0.000496 ***
Residuals     161 27.618   0.1715
---

      Chickpea   Cereal Sugarbeet   Cabbage
         5         137         18         6

      Crop Plants NodulesLg visregFit visregLwr visregUpr
1 Chickpea      2  1.337431  1.7540283  1.3882475  2.1198091
2  Cereal      2  1.337431  1.3437446  1.2718354  1.4156538
3 Sugarbeet   2  1.337431  0.9628836  0.7683778  1.1573894
4  Cabbage    2  1.337431  0.5724377  0.2296551  0.9152202

Backtransformed

      Crop Plants NodulesLg visregFit visregLwr visregUpr
1 Chickpea      2  1.337431  55.758162  23.4482354  130.767751
2  Cereal      2  1.337431  21.067067  17.6997344  25.040768
3 Sugarbeet   2  1.337431   8.180865  4.8664828  13.367771
4  Cabbage    2  1.337431   2.736265  0.6968957   7.226597

```

Lentil Fig. 4B

```

~~~~~
PlantDW ~ NodulesLg + Plants
~~~~~

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  2.76692    0.06838  40.465 <2e-16 ***
NodulesLg    0.27961    0.02157  12.960 <2e-16 ***
Plants      -0.02604    0.03705  -0.703  0.483
---

Residual standard error: 0.1262 on 164 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.5234,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.5176
F-statistic: 90.07 on 2 and 164 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16

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              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
NodulesLg     1  2.8592   2.8592  179.646 <2e-16 ***
Plants         1  0.0079   0.0079   0.494  0.483
Residuals     164  2.6102   0.0159
---

```

Lentil Fig. 4C

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~~~~~
NodulesLg ~ Latitude + Plants
~~~~~

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  9.20498    2.09737   4.389 2.03e-05 ***
Latitude     -0.23541    0.05466  -4.307 2.84e-05 ***
Plants        0.45138    0.12231   3.690 0.000304 ***
---

Residual standard error: 0.4328 on 164 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1881,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.1782
F-statistic: 18.99 on 2 and 164 DF,  p-value: 3.807e-08

```

```

              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
Latitude      1  4.565    4.565   24.37 1.94e-06 ***
Plants        1  2.551    2.551   13.62 0.000304 ***
Residuals     164 30.719    0.187
---

```

```

Lentil Fig. 4D ~~~~~
NodulesLg ~ Longitude + Plants
~~~~~

Coefficients:
      Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) -6.00835    0.95506  -6.291 2.76e-09 ***
Longitude    0.17825    0.02657   6.708 3.05e-10 ***
Plants       0.47582    0.11326   4.201 4.35e-05 ***
---

Residual standard error: 0.4045 on 164 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.2908,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.2822
F-statistic: 33.62 on 2 and 164 DF,  p-value: 5.79e-13

      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value    Pr(>F)
Longitude  1  8.115   8.115  49.60 4.93e-11 ***
Plants     1  2.888   2.888  17.65 4.35e-05 ***
Residuals 164 26.832   0.164
---
    
```

Table S4 Selection of literature reporting chickpea nodule numbers per plant for a range of contexts, inoculation methods and growth periods.

Source	Context	Nodules/plant	Comments
Biabani <i>et al.</i> 2011	Greenhouse	21-101	Inoculated with culture suspension to growth medium before planting; grown 7 weeks (number mean of 6 reps)
Elkoca <i>et al.</i> 2015	Greenhouse	1-32	Inoculated with peat slurry to dry seed presowing; grown 12-13 weeks; grown 45 days
Gebremariam & Tesfay 2021	Review	8-43	Various contextst in source papers
İçgen <i>et al.</i> 2002	Growth chamber	73-98	Leonard jars inoculated with rhizobial suspension; grown 30 days
Oparah <i>et al.</i> 2024	Greenhouse	1-5	Inoculated with cultures suspension to seedings; grown 6 weeks
Plett <i>et al.</i> 2021	Growth chamber	13-89	Inoculated with culture suspension to 2-week old seedings in vermiculite; grown 6 weeks
Rathjen <i>et al.</i> 2024	Field	1-9	Inoculated with peat slurry to dry seed presowing; grown 12-13 weeks
Rehan <i>et al.</i> 2018	Field	59-75	Seed inoculated; flowering stage 139 days
Wubie and Adal 2021	Greenhouse	15-69	Inoculated with culture suspension 3 days after transplanting seedlings; grown 50 days
Xu <i>et al.</i> 2022	Greenhouse	1-95	Inoculated with culture suspension to 7-day old transplants; grown 6-16 weeks (higher numbers in older plants)

Supplementary References

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